

WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT ELEMENTS IN "SAM ANTEP GILAM" LLC.

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Abstract. *In this article analysis of modern marketing-management principles and elements, study of the formation of marketing management, description of the enterprise's production activities, analysis of the assortment, price, movement system, quality and competitiveness of goods produced in the enterprise.*

Keywords: *economy, market, enterprise, competition, commodity, assortment, displacement, quality, analysis.*

INTRODUCTION. In the strategy of the rapid development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, great importance is attached to the textile and sewing industry. The reason for this is, on the one hand, the creation of products with a high added value as a result of deep processing of raw cotton, and on the other hand, the great potential of the textile industry in increasing the export potential of our country. The adoption of Decree No. PF-5285 by the President of our country on December 14, 2017 "On measures for rapid development of the textile and sewing-knitting industry" serves as a legal basis for the development of the industry.

Analysis of literature on the topic Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application. Among them, we include famous scientists such as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall possible

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the research carried out in the field of marketing in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. R. Ibragimov to them. Yo. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodzhaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodzhaeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results For the purpose of our scientific research on the market of carpet products It consists in developing practical recommendations for improving the marketing management activities in the joint venture "SAM ANTEP GILAM" LLC, including the organization of the product policy, the implementation of the assortment policy, the management of the product life cycle, and the improvement of competitiveness in the domestic and foreign markets. To achieve these goals, the following tasks were advanced and resolved:

-Critical analysis of modern marketing-management principles, elements and theoretical foundations;

- to study the formation of marketing management of enterprises in the conditions of economic liberalization and modernization;

- To describe the production activity of the joint venture "SAM ANTEP GILAM" LLC;

- assessing the assortment, price, movement system, quality and competitiveness of goods produced in the enterprise;

"SamAntepGilam" Foreign Enterprise Limited Liability Company also tries to fulfill the tasks set by the President and saturate the market with quality carpet products.

"SAG" LLC is one of the leading enterprises in Uzbekistan in the field of carpet production, taking into account the great changes taking place in the modernizing economy of Uzbekistan.

SAG Carpets is a carpet and rug manufacturer, and during this period it has come a long way from a small textile factory to a leading enterprise in Central Asia and CIS countries.

The SAG trademark is a guarantee of the use of the most advanced technologies and regular quality control in the carpet industry. The entire production cycle, starting from the production of yarn and ending with the final packaging of the product, is carried out in the factory itself. The enterprise uses only high-quality and environmentally friendly raw materials. Also, the ISO 9001:2008 international quality control system has been introduced, which is a guarantee of compliance of our products with all international norms and quality standards. The enterprise is equipped with the most innovative equipment from Belgium and Germany, such as Schoner Wohnen and VanDeWiele.

SAG is one of the largest employers in the Republic of Uzbekistan. A cohesive and organized team always sets great goals for itself and always achieves success on the way to its goals.

The company's plan is to increase production by purchasing more innovative equipment, increasing new jobs and increasing the number of collections we offer.

The main goal of the company is to bring joy, comfort and convenience to people's lives by providing a wide selection of high-quality carpet products.

Table 1

Dynamics of economic indicators of "SAG" LLC

	2000	2005	2010	2016	2020	2022
Introduction of modern equipment	1	12	25	30	35	40
Production dynamics (thousand, m2)	1000	7000	12000	18000	20000	30000
Number of employees	50	200	500	700	900	1000

The company has its own laboratory, which was founded in 2012. 30-35 tons of dyeing agents are produced in the laboratory for 1 month. It is the only carpet enterprise in Uzbekistan with its own dyeing agents laboratory.

The enterprise spins up to 38 tons of yarn per day. This enterprise is one of the first enterprises to start production of polypropylene yarns (PP BCF, PP HS, PP HS FREEZE, TRICOLOR YARNS) in our country.

The production of textile yarns was launched in 2016, and about 350 workers are currently working in this direction. On average, up to 2.5 tons of cotton fibers are processed per year. It is

one of the enterprises founded for the production of textile yarns consisting of a mixture of cotton and artificial fibers.

Figure 1. Yarn production process at the enterprise.

In addition, the enterprise also produces polyester yarn, which was founded in 2016. The annual production volume is 3.5 tons, and the production of polyester yarn is carried out by processing polyethylene bottles.

This enterprise has penetrated not only the national market but also the foreign market by offering its high quality carpets and rugs. Currently, the company exports its products to all CIS countries (Russia, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Azerbaijan, etc.) and countries such as China and Turkey. The export potential of the enterprise is very high.

The analysis of marketing management is carried out in accordance with the concept of marketing-mix presented in the theoretical part of our research, that is, product (product assortment), price (price policy), place (sales organization) and promotion (marketing communications). In addition, in the analysis of marketing management, we have also considered the company's policy towards employees separately.

A) product range and its analysis

Product assortment development is the most important function of enterprise marketing. It is manifested in the application of the traditional or hidden technical and material capabilities of the manufacturer to products and services that have a certain consumer value, satisfy the customer and benefit the enterprise.

The assortment of products includes various carpets, carpets, rugs and other types of rugs, which differ in their composition, production technology, density, pile length, size, appearance, design and other technical parameters.

TodaySAG joint venture in order to expand the range of carpets sold in the markets of the republic and to meet the demand of consumersMore than 3000 designs included in about 30 collectionsThe production of carpets has been launched.Including "Tumaris", "Zilli", "Rodin", "Zara", "Troya", "Iran", "Sheikh", "Pantera", "Shahsultan", "Imperial", "Avangard", "Super shaggy", "Isfahan", "Avangard", "Babi", "Imperial coffee" collections and others. The collections here are different in design. Carpets produced in different colors, mainly 8 colors, and thus the designs of the collections are different from each other.

Table 2

"Sam Antep Carpet" JVParticipation of LLC products in the company's income.

Collection name	In revenue share	In growth mode
Isfahan	19.45%	19.45%
Tumaris	18.39%	37.84%
Rodin Gray	11.40%	49.24%
Zilly	9.86%	59.1%
Emir	6.98%	66.08%
Ponte	5.24%	71.32%
Reflex	4.62%	75.94%
Therapy	4.61%	80.55%
Vanguard	2.89%	83.44%
Baby	2.87%	86.31%
X(20 others)	13.69%	100%
General	100.00%	

Table 3

"Sam Antep Carpet" JVAssessment of the importance of LLC products for the company

Collection name	In revenue share	In growth mode	Grouping
Isfahan	19.45%	19.45%	A
Tumaris	18.39%	37.84%	A
Rodin Gray	11.40%	49.24%	A
Zilly	9.86%	59.1%	A
Emir	6.98%	66.08%	A
Ponte	5.24%	71.32%	A
Reflex	4.62%	75.94%	A
Therapy	4.61%	80.55%	B
Vanguard	2.89%	83.44%	B
Baby	2.87%	86.31%	B
X(20 others)	13.69%	100%	B.C
General	100.00%		

In our case, group A (15-80% by law) Sheikh, Imperial, Iran, Aladin, Almira, Zara, Fortuna (23% of the range) accounted for 75.94% of the total revenue, group B and group C Super Shaggy, Troy , Imperial Gray and 20 other collections made up the rest of the revenue. It can be seen that collections in group A are the main sources of income for the company.

By dividing the products into such groups, the enterprise can have a report that will determine exactly which group of products is the main source of income.

"Sam Antep Carpet" JVLLC products in the company's incomeAnother area of focus is the pattern and color combination of rugs. In recent years, we have started to produce carpets of any size according to the wishes of the tailor, that is, we have introduced work on individual orders. Our task today is to introduce the production of carpets of different shapes (round, oval, complex shapes). In this case, it will be possible to fully satisfy the design requirements of consumers.

Another aspect of the brand policy is to increase the weaving density of carpets, that is, to increase the softness and functionality of carpets. In this direction, the policy aimed at the modernization of production by the management of the enterprise can be mentioned. Today, he is working on investment projects for further improvement of production. Areas such as increasing the types of threads used in carpets, ensuring color stability, and expanding the assortment of carpet products are also separate aspects of the policy of improving the quality of our products.

Developed market relations do not exist without innovation, therefore the enterprise pays great attention to scientific research and tries to implement the results of scientific research.

B) Price policy and its analysis

"Sam Antep Carpet" JV The price policy of the LLC is based on the functional purpose of the manufactured products and the purpose of purchase. In this case, the classification of the company's products into categories is the main criterion for determining their price.

A-category: Products that confirm their position for the consumer, are recognized as home decoration, are produced from high-quality raw materials and have individual properties. Usually, these products are part of the collection and are directed to satisfy the demand of each consumer;

V-type: made of high-quality raw materials, distinguished by its design. but products intended for the upper and middle income strata of the population, which include mass design and fashionable product batches;

S-category: Mass-produced carpet products tailored to the needs of the population. Their main feature is the orientation of consumers to the bulk price, the harmony of price and quality, and the promptness of order fulfillment.

Category D. Carpets and bedding products for public places, enterprises and organizations.

For each category of products "Sam Antep Carpet" JV LLC company creates its own price policy. The prices of some of the products produced by the company in 2021 are presented in the table below (Table 4).

Table 4

Market price of "SAG" LLC carpets as of April 1, 2021

t/r	Collection name	VAT is yours	with VAT (retail price)
1	Isfahan	373300	485300
2	Tumaris	324700	422050
3	Rodin Gray	243300	316250
4	Zilly	132200	158700
5	Emir	133300	160000
6	Ponte	248000	330050
7	Reflex	135600	165600
8	Therapy	243300	316250
9	Vanguard	99700	119600
10	Baby	99700	119700

In the production of the company's price policy, attention is mainly paid to the prices of competitors, on the other hand, it is shown that the company works in the conditions agreed with the partners in the republic and abroad.

V) Analysis of the distribution policy

"SAG" LLC joint venture has been leading the carpet market in all aspects. Up to now, carpet products of this enterprise are sold in more than 500 sales points across the territory of Uzbekistan.

"SAG" joint venture has its own official dealers and stores in each region, their number is more than 20. , Termiz, Namangan, Andijan, Fergana, Kokan, Jizzah, Gulistan.

Table 5

Official dealers and stores of "SAG" LLC

No	City name	Store name	Address
1	Tashkent	"THE WORLD OF SAG CARPETS"	Koksaroy street, Tahtka bazar
2		"SAG CARPETS"	TXY, Bek-tupi Shopping Complex
3		"SAG"	Koshbegi massif, KXY street 14
4		"SAG"	Bardavom street 27, Chinabad
5		"IDEA HOME"	TXY Street, Med Gorodok
6		"SAG"	Chilonzor, Bogiston street 4A
7	Samarkand	"SAG"	229 Rudaki Street
8	Navoi	"SAG"	Victory Avenue, 197
9	Bukhara	"SAG"	11, Khujanurabad Street
10	Urganch	"SAG"	Devotees 1 house 1
11	Defect	"SAG"	J. Aymirzaeva, 93
12	Opposite	"SAG"	Uzbekistan street 405
13	We sweat	"SAG"	Progress 47A
14	Namangan	"SAG"	Girvonsoy, 11
15	Andijan	"SAG" Kashmir shop	Independence 21
16		"SAG"	Kusharik Dasakhi Street 1
17	Ferghana	"SAG"	24 Joydam Street
18	Kokan	"SAG"	A. Novoi street 147A
19	Jizzah	"SAG"	Quiet market
20	Gulistan	"SAG"	Neighborhood array

G) Policy of moving goods in the market.

Advertising and communication policy of "SAG" LLC joint venture is aimed at providing more information to consumers. First of all, electronic media is used, the company's website (<https://www.sag.uz/uz>), Telegram, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter social media pages and channels. The company also attaches great importance to outdoor advertising. Due to the functions

and characteristics of carpet products, the company has been paying great attention to expanding relations with wholesale customers. Communication policy is one of the main tasks of the marketing department of the enterprise. The joint venture "SAG" LLC also tries to establish trading houses abroad. For example, on March 9, 2020 The opening ceremony of "SAG" Uzbek carpets and "Gulnor" silk products trading house was held in New York. According to the Embassy of Uzbekistan in the USA, this trading house is the second exhibition area of Uzbek national light industrial products in the USA. Before that, a similar trading center was opened in the city of Philadelphia in 2019.

The results of the analysis showed that "SamAntepGilam" LLC has developed a unique approach to marketing management, that is, technologically and technically surpassing competitors and guaranteeing product quality. Taking into account that this approach was effective during the establishment of the enterprise, even today it contributes to the success of the enterprise in the carpet sales market.

But today, sudden changes in the national and foreign market environment and the complexity of the behavior of potential consumers create a need for development in marketing activities. This requires greater attention to customer communication, sales and after-sales processes.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Modern marketing activity has become the main tool for increasing competitiveness in the world market, therefore it is necessary to ensure the use of the most advanced marketing technologies in front of Uzbekistan's enterprises. It is especially important to increase the marketing efficiency in the production of weaving and knitting products, which is one of the strong sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan. The relevance of this mammo is confirmed by a number of Decrees and Decisions adopted by our honorable President in recent years. The need to increase the effectiveness of marketing in enterprises was the goal of our research conducted in our dissertation and is the basis for the following conclusions.

1. The modern concept of marketing includes production marketing as well as social ethical marketing (social goals, organizational culture, corporate responsibility), marketing of new ideas (information technology, consumer, scientific and technical development), emotional behavioral marketing (purchase process, consumption process, purchase motivation), marketing-mix ("4R" marketing, "7R" marketing, "15R" marketing), logistics marketing (marketing and logistics integration, procurement management, customer management);

2. In these concepts, the concept of marketing management or marketing-mix is universal compared to others and is considered convenient and effective for manufacturing enterprises. The famous "4R" principle has been accepted as a symbol of marketing management in almost all fields. At the same time, in recent years, the penetration of marketing into the field of transactions has prompted the development of additional principles, that is, led to the concept of "7R".

3. The textile sector of Uzbekistan is one of the drivers of our country's international competitiveness. In recent years, as a result of the processing of raw cotton in our country, great changes have taken place in the textile and sewing industry. In particular, the development of the number of carpet weaving enterprises leads to increased competition in the market of carpet products.

4. Management of marketing activities in the joint venture "SAM ANTEP GILAM" is based on the above principles and includes product quality and assortment, price, sales

technology, and the processes of moving goods on the market. At the same time, the focus on production has a negative impact on competitiveness in the market.

The theoretical and practical research carried out above requires attention to additional principles in the marketing management of the joint venture "SAM ANTEP GILAM". In our opinion, the market policy aspects of marketing management should be focused on three principles of the company: people, sales process and sales environment development. Implementation of the proposed principles will increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the joint venture "SAM ANTEP GILAM".

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